

Effect of addition of sodium bicarbonate/carbonate on the rate of photocatalytic bleaching of methylene blue over CdS powder

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The photocatalytic bleaching of methylene blue over CdS powder was carried out in the presence and absence of sodium bicarbonate/carbonate. A comparison was made between the rate of photobleaching of methylene blue with and without bicarbonate or carbonate ions. It was observed that the photobleaching was more efficient in the presence of bicarbonate or carbonate ions. The effects of various parameters have been observed and a tentative mechanism for the photobleaching has been proposed.

Our rivers are polluted by effluent water from dyeing and printing industries. This creates a problem for aquatic life. Photocatalytic transformation converts the coloured water into colourless water. Semiconductor powders suspended in solution can be employed to carry out heterogeneous photocatalytic and photosynthetic processes. Cadmium sulfide¹ is an effective photocatalyst because it has the desired band gap and can be utilized to initiate or to drive a particular chemical reaction in a desired direction. Efforts have been made to modify the semiconducting CdS powder² in such a way that its photocatalytic activity is enhanced. The photocatalytic activity of CdS is likely to be affected by doping with *3d* transition metal ions, heat treatment with alkali metal halides, addition of bicarbonate and carbonate ions, etc. A little is known about such modifications, and therefore, there is a pressing demand to scan the effect of certain modifications on the photocatalytic behavior of CdS powder. This gave us a momentum to carry out the proposed work.

Sayama and Awakawa³ reported that the addition of a large quantity of carbonate salts, such as Na₂CO₃, K₂CO₃ and NaHCO₃ to a Pt-TiO₂ suspension leads to efficient photocatalytic decomposition of water in liquid phase. They further reported⁴ that the activities of most of the catalysts increase on the addition of carbonate salts. They studied⁵ the effect of carbonate and bicarbonate addition on the photocatalytic decomposition of liquid water over a ZrO₂ catalyst. Turek *et al.*⁶ reported that the ZrO₂ surface easily adsorbs bicarbonate under a CO₂ atmosphere. The activities of NiO_x-SrTiO₃⁷, NiO_x-TiO₂⁸ and RhO_x-SrTiO₃⁹ increase on the addition of a large amount of NaOH in contrast with ZrO₂.

Results and discussion

The plots of (1 + log O.D) vs exposure time were found to be straight-lines, which indicates that the photocatalytic bleaching of methylene blue follows pseudo-first order kinetics. The rate constant (*k*) for the reaction were determined using the expression, $k = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$.

A comparison was made of the rate of photocatalytic bleaching of methylene blue with and without sodium bicarbonate and sodium carbonate. It was observed that the photobleaching was more efficient in the presence of bicarbonate or carbonate ions, as reflected by the values of the rate constants (without NaHCO₃, $k = 2.32 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and with NaHCO₃, $k = 3.35 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ also without Na₂CO₃, $k = 1.50 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and with Na₂CO₃, $k = 1.82 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$).

Effect of NaHCO₃ and Na₂CO₃ concentration :

The effect of variation of concentration of sodium bicarbonate or sodium carbonate was studied by taking different concentration of bicarbonate or carbonate solution (Table 1).

Table 1

[Methylene blue] = $1.66 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, pH = 6.5, CdS = 0.08 g, light intensity = 30.0 mW cm⁻²

[NaHCO ₃] × 10 ³ M	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁵ s ⁻¹	[Na ₂ CO ₃] × 10 ³ M	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁵ s ⁻¹
1.00	7.02	0.50	3.72
1.31	7.87	1.02	3.81
2.00	10.79	1.28	5.30
3.98	8.32	2.01	4.52
6.61	7.81	2.78	4.29
9.97	7.68	4.02	3.38

The rate of photocatalytic bleaching of methylene blue increased on increasing the concentration of bicarbonate or carbonate ions to a certain limit, while a reverse trend was observed beyond this limit. Bicarbonate or carbonate species may react with holes during the process, which ultimately leads to charge separation, thus restricting the recombination of electron with holes. Enhancement in the concentration of bicarbonate or carbonate will provide more hole traps and as a consequence, the reaction rate increases. However, on increasing the concentration of bicarbonate or carbonate anions beyond the limit, semiconductor surface may have a multilayer of bicarbonate or carbonate ions instead of a monolayer. The formation of multilayer will not permit the bicarbonate ions on the surface to act as hole trap and thus a corresponding decrease in the rate of the reaction.

Effect of pH :

The effect of pH on the photobleaching of methylene blue was also studied (Table 2).

Table 2

[Methylene blue] = 1.66×10^{-5} M, CdS = 0.08 g, light intensity = 30.0 mW cm⁻²

pH	$k \times 10^4$ s ⁻¹	
	2.00×10^{-3} M NaHCO ₃	1.28×10^{-3} M Na ₂ CO ₃
6.0	1.06	0.49
6.5	1.08	0.53
7.0	1.19	0.61
7.5	1.28	0.62
8.0	1.34	0.58
8.5	1.31	0.57

It was observed that the rate of the reaction increased with increase in pH to an optimum value. On further increasing pH of the medium, the reaction rate decreases. This can be explained on the basis that bicarbonate or carbonate ions are more stable in the pH range in the alkaline solution and therefore, the reaction rate increases on increasing the pH and it reaches an optimum value for bicarbonate (pH 8.0) and carbonate (pH 7.5). On increasing the pH above this limit, the concentration of OH⁻ ions will also increase; thus, creating a competition for adsorption between OH⁻ ions with that of HCO₃⁻ or CO₃²⁻ ions, where OH⁻ ions will get an edge due to smaller size and large charge density. Hence, HCO₃⁻ or CO₃²⁻ ions will not act as hole trap as effectively as earlier in the presence of OH⁻ ions and a corresponding decrease in the rate of the reaction was observed.

Effect of methylene blue concentration :

The rate of photocatalytic bleaching was found to de-

crease with increasing concentration of methylene blue (Table 3). This may be attributed to the fact that the increasing concentration of methylene blue imparts a dark blue colour to the solution and it may act as a filter to the incident light reaching the semiconductor surface. As a consequence, the rate of photocatalytic bleaching of methylene blue decreases.

Table 3

pH = 8.0 (with NaHCO₃), pH = 7.5 (with Na₂CO₃), CdS = 0.08 g, light intensity = 30.0 mW cm⁻²

[Methylene blue] $\times 10^5$ M	$k \times 10^4$ s ⁻¹	
	2.00×10^{-3} M NaHCO ₃	1.28×10^{-3} M Na ₂ CO ₃
1.10	2.06	0.77
1.25	1.59	0.75
1.42	1.46	0.65
1.66	1.34	0.62
2.00	1.25	0.60
2.50	0.98	0.53

Effect of amount of semiconductor :

The results of the effect of amount of semiconductor on the photocatalytic bleaching of methylene blue are reported in Table 4. The rate of photocatalytic bleaching increased with increasing amount of CdS. This may be explained on the basis that the number of exposed semiconducting particles will increase as the amount of semiconductor powder was increased and in turn, the number of electron-hole pairs will also increase. This will result into the corresponding increase in the rate of the reaction. The saturation like behavior was not observed in this case. This may be due to the fact that the bicarbonate or carbonate ions remain in the bulk of the solution as well as on the surface of all the semiconductor particles of the complete layer.

Table 4

pH = 8.0 (with NaHCO₃), pH = 7.5 (with Na₂CO₃), [Methylene blue] = 1.25×10^{-5} M, light intensity = 30.0 mW cm⁻²

Amount of semiconductor g	$k \times 10^4$ s ⁻¹	
	2.00×10^{-3} M NaHCO ₃	1.28×10^{-3} M Na ₂ CO ₃
0.06	1.33	0.68
0.08	1.59	0.75
0.10	2.06	0.84
0.12	2.07	1.48
0.14	3.03	1.54
0.16	3.79	1.56

Effect of light intensity :

The light intensity also affects the rate of photocatalytic bleaching of methylene blue and the results are presented in Table 5. The data reveal that increase in the light intensity increases the rate of the reaction. The increasing light intensity will increase the number of photons striking the CdS particles per unit area per second and as a result more electron-hole pairs are generated. This results in an overall increase in the rate of the reaction. However, at higher light intensities, the thermal side reaction may also start and hence, the rate of photocatalytic bleaching show a decreasing behavior.

Table 5

[Methylene blue] = $1.25 \times 10^{-5} M$, CdS = 0.10 g (with NaHCO₃), CdS = 0.12 g (with Na₂CO₃), pH = 8.0 (with NaHCO₃), pH = 7.5 (with Na₂CO₃)

Light intensity mW cm ⁻²	$k \times 10^4 s^{-1}$	
	$2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ NaHCO ₃	$1.28 \times 10^{-3} M$ Na ₂ CO ₃
30.0	2.06	1.48
40.0	2.49	1.52
50.0	2.59	1.77
60.0	3.35	1.82
70.0	3.22	1.63
80.0	2.05	1.62

Mechanism :

On the basis of the experimental observations and corroborating existing literature, a tentative mechanism has been proposed for the photocatalytic bleaching of methylene blue with CdS powder in the presence of sodium bicarbonate or sodium carbonate.

Dye absorbs photon and converts it into its singlet excited state which via inter-system crossing will change into its triplet excited state. The semiconductor (SC) excites on exposure to give excited state (SC*), which will generate an electron-hole pair. The electron from the valence band is promoted to the conduction band, leaving behind a hole in the valence band. This hole reacts with bicarbonate species on the cadmium sulfide surface and as a result, bicarbonate radical is formed. This reaction accelerates the charge separation of electron and hole because a surface bicarbonate anion acts as a trap for holes. The bicarbonate radical dissociates into H⁺ and carbonate anion radical (CO₃^{•-}). In case of carbonate ions, the hole is trapped to give CO₃^{•-}. Such two carbonate anion radicals couple to give peroxy carbonate species (C₂O₆²⁻), which is easily decomposed into O₂ and CO₂ by the reaction with two holes. The surface of CdS particles is covered with bicarbonate or carbonate species on addition of bicarbonate or carbonate salts, respectively. It may be considered that these bicarbonate or carbonate species on semiconductor surface play an important role in the desorption of oxygen via the carbonate anion radical. The electron in the conduction band will react with triplet excited state of dye and convert it into its leuco form, which will ultimately degrade into final decomposition products.

Experimental

Stock solutions of methylene blue ($1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$), sodium bicarbonate (0.02 M) and sodium carbonate (0.02 M) were prepared in double-distilled water. In the first set, 7.5 ml of methylene blue, 6.0 ml of sodium bicarbonate and 46.5 ml water were mixed. The pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted to 8.0 and 0.10 g of cadmium sulfide was added. In the second set, 7.5 ml of dye, 4.0 ml of sodium carbonate and 48.5 ml of water were mixed. The pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted at 7.5 and 0.12 g of CdS was added to it. These reaction mixtures were exposed to a 200 W tungsten lamp (Phillips, light intensity = 30.0 mW cm⁻²). The intensity of light at various distances from the lamp was measured with the help of suryamapi CEL 201 solarimeter. A water filter was used to cut off thermal radiation. pH of the solution was measured by a Systronics 335 pH meter. The desired pH of the solution was adjusted by the addition of previously standardized sulfuric acid and sodium hydroxide. The progress of the reaction was measured spectrophotometrically at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 660 \text{ nm}$ using a JASCO 7800 spectrophotometer.

References

1. K. T. Ranjit, R. Krishnamoorthy, T. K. Varadarajan and

- B. Viswanathan, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. (A)*, 1995, **86**, 185;
F. Borgarello, K. Kalyansundaram, M. Gratzel and E. Pelizzetti,
Helv. Chim. Acta, 1982, **65**, 243.
2. M. M. Taqui Khan, R. C. Bhardwaj and C. Bhardwaj, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 1; K. Kobayakawa, T. Miura, A. Suzuki, Y. Sato and A. Fujishima, *Solar Energy Mater. Solar Cells*, 1993, **30**, 201.
 3. K. Sayama and H. Arakawa, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1992, 150.
 4. K. Sayama and H. Arakawa, *Chem. Lett.*, 1992, 253; *J. Photochem. Photobiol. (A)*, 1994, **77**, 243.
 5. K. Sayama and H. Arakawa, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. (A)*, 1996, **94**, 67.
 6. A. M. Turek, I. W. Wachs and E. Deccanio, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1992, **96**, 5000.
 7. K. Domen, A. Kudo and T. Onishi, *J. Catal.*, 1986, **102**, 92.
 8. A. Kudo, K. Domen, K. Maruya and T. Onishi, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1987, **133**, 517.
 9. J. Lehn, J. Sauvage, R. Ziessel and L. Hilaire, *Isr. J. Chem.*, 1982, **22**, 168.